

Lumpy Skin Disease

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Introduction

The virus that causes lumpy skin disease (LSD) is called the lumpy skin disease virus (LSDV), and it belongs to the Capripoxvirus genus of the Poxviridae family. It is a transboundary disease of the economic importance affecting cattle and water buffaloes. High morbidity and low mortality are the results of the disease, which is spread by arthropod vectors. LSD recently made headlines for the first time in India with a morbidity rate of 7.1% in cattle. The disease is endemic to countries in Africa and the Middle East, but it has recently begun to spread to Asia and other continents. Recent reports came from Bangladesh and China, two countries that share borders with India. The disease's epidemiological situation is currently unknown in India. The disease might be stopped from spreading with the help of vaccination, strict quarantine rules, and vector control.

Lumpy Skin Disease (LSD) in Cow
Multiple skin nodules over the entire skin

Transmission

The virus is thought to persist in skin lesions or nodules for a long time and has a strong affinity for dermal tissues, making them the most significant sources of infection for healthy animals. The virus can also be passed on to susceptible cattle through the blood, saliva, semen, nasal and lachrymal secretions, milk, and saliva of infected animals (transmissible to suckling calves). Nodules that are appearing on the mucous membranes of the eyes, nose, mouth, rectum, udder and genitalia also ulcerate and shed viruses, which can serve as sources of infections. Animals those are viraemic are a significant source of infection, especially when the infection can last for up to two weeks.

As a result, the virus is transmitted to the hosts through arthropods that feed on blood, such as biting flies, mosquitoes, and ticks. Additionally, to direct contact, contamination of feed and water can also cause transmission. Iatrogenic transmission or spread can also happen when several animals are being vaccinated at once with a single syringe and needle. In this situation, the needle can infect healthy animals with the virus by injecting it into crusts and other skin lesions. A variety of can mechanically transmit LSDV.

Clinical signs

The incubation period of this disease is 4–14 days. Around 50% of susceptible cattle exhibit the recognisable nodules on the skin and mucous membranes after developing fever, lacrimation,

nasal discharge, anorexia, and hypersalivation. The entire cutis as well as the mucosa of the GI, respiratory, and genital tracts are affected by the nodules, which are well-circumscribed, round, slightly raised, firm, and painful. On the muzzle, as well as in the mucous membranes of the nose and mouth, nodules can form. A solid, creamy-grey or yellow mass of tissue is present in the skin nodules. Oedema forms in the udder, brisket, and legs, and regional lymph nodes swell.

When a secondary infection happens, there may be extensive suppuration and sloughing, which causes the animal to lose a lot of weight. In time, the nodules either regress or necrosis of the skin produces hard, raised areas that are distinct from the surrounding skin (referred to as "sit-fasts"). These regions slough off, leaving ulcers that heal and leave scars. The disease's clinical manifestations also include decreased milk production, abortion, infertility, and sometimes death. Mortality is typically low, and morbidity ranges from 5% to 50%. The biggest loss occurs as a result of decreased milk production, loss of condition, rejection, or decreased value of the hide.

Diagnosis

Virus isolation, polymerase chain reaction (PCR), and histopathology are all methods for making a confirmatory diagnosis of disease. The disease may be confused with the less clinically important pseudo-lumpy skin disease, which is caused by a herpesvirus (bovine herpesvirus 2). Although the herpesvirus lesions appear to be limited to the teats and udder of cows in some regions of the world, where the disease is known as bovine herpes mammillitis, these diseases can be clinically similar. The difference between pseudo-lumpy skin disease and true lumpy skin disease is mainly determined by the isolation and/or identification of the causative virus. Electron microscopy can show the poxvirus in the early skin lesions of lumpy skin disease. The two diseases can be distinguished by PCR (polymerase chain reaction).

Treatment and prevention

LSD is only symptomatically treated, and antimicrobial therapy is used to stop secondary bacterial complications. Combining antimicrobials, anti-inflammatory drugs, supportive therapy, and anti-septic solutions has been successful in treating LSD complications and saving lives. However, treating LSD (and its complications) is expensive and does not always result in full recovery; for these reasons, prevention is preferable to mitigating the significant economic losses brought on by hide damage, milk loss from mastitis, and loss of animal product due to death, abortion, fever, and myiasis.

According to the report only live attenuated vaccines against LSD are available and it observed that homologous vaccines are more effective than sheep pox strain vaccines. At the farm level, a careful surveillance of the disease's onset and spread is to be undertaken. There is a significant risk of spreading the disease to the local herd if new animals are purchased that are either sick or viraemic but not showing any symptoms. There should be some restriction on adding new animals to herds. It is best to only purchase stock from reliable sources. Prior to movement and upon arrival, new animals should be checked for clinical signs and declared free of them. They should then be quarantined or kept apart from the herd for at least 28 days.

Cattle herds in affected villages should be kept apart from other herds by refraining from communal grazing. To reduce the chance of the disease being spread by a vector, cattle should be treated with insect repellents on a regular basis. Although it cannot completely stop

transmission, this measure may lower the risk. Reducing the number of vectors on and around cattle is a sustainable, affordable, and environmentally friendly process that involves limiting vector breeding sites like standing water sources, slurry, and manure, as well as improving drainage in holdings.

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